

Search(es) for $b \rightarrow s\tau\tau$ decays at the LHCb experiment

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Abstract

Searches for the rare decays $B^0 \rightarrow K^+\pi^-\tau^+\tau^-$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow K^+K^-\tau^+\tau^-$ have been performed using 5.4fb^{-1} of pp collisions collected with the LHCb detector during 2016–2018. Tau leptons are identified through the decay $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^-\bar{\nu}_\mu\nu_\tau$. No significant excess above background expectations is observed, and upper limits on the branching fractions are set in bins of dihadron invariant mass. From these, upper limits on the resonant modes $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0}(892)\tau^+\tau^-$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi(1020)\tau^+\tau^-$ are also set, to 2.8×10^{-4} and 4.7×10^{-4} at 95% confidence level respectively. These results provide the most stringent constraints to date on $b \rightarrow s\tau^+\tau^-$ transitions.

1 Introduction

Rare decays mediated by the flavour-changing neutral-current (FCNC) transition $b \rightarrow s\ell^+\ell^-$ are highly suppressed in the Standard Model (SM), which makes them an excellent probe for new physics beyond the SM. In recent years, measurements of the muonic FCNC transitions $b \rightarrow s\mu^+\mu^-$ have shown deviations from SM expectations [1–10] in the form of tensions in branching fractions and discrepancies in angular observables.

In the charged-current sector, measurements of the ratios $R(D)$ and $R(D^*)$ have also shown persistent deviations from SM predictions [11–22]. In light of these measurements several classes of new physics models predict substantial enhancements to $b \rightarrow s\tau^+\tau^-$ transitions, in some cases enhancing the branching fraction by up to three orders of magnitude above the SM expectation of $\mathcal{O}(10^{-7})$ [23–31]. The possibility of such enhancements in new physics scenarios provides strong motivation for dedicated searches in channels involving tau leptons. Prior to the analysis described in these proceedings, the tightest experimental constraint was obtained by the Belle II collaboration with $\mathcal{B}(B^0 \rightarrow K^*(892)^0\tau^+\tau^-) < 1.8 \times 10^{-3}$ at 90% confidence level (CL) [32]. In parallel with the present analysis, the Belle II collaboration also obtained $\mathcal{B}(B^+ \rightarrow K^+\tau^+\tau^-) < 8.7 \times 10^{-4}$ at 90% CL [33]. At LHCb, searches for the decay $B_s^0 \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ in 2011–2012 data yielded upper limits of 6.8×10^{-3} at 95% CL [34], where tau decays to three pions were considered. Searches for rescattering effects in $B^0 \rightarrow K^*(892)^0\mu^+\mu^-$ decays also resulted in an upper limit on the Wilson coefficient $|\mathcal{C}_9^{\tau\tau}|$ of 600 at 95% CL [8].

The analysis described in these proceedings [35] constitutes the first search by the LHCb collaboration for the decays $B^0 \rightarrow K^+\pi^-\tau^+\tau^-$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow K^+K^-\tau^+\tau^-$. The study uses the muonic decays $\tau^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu\bar{\nu}_\tau$. This choice benefits from excellent muon triggering and identification at the LHCb experiment [36]. The downside is the presence of four neutrinos in the final state, which precludes reconstruction of the B -meson invariant mass and limits the power of kinematic constraints. In contrast, three-prong pionic tau decays offer information regarding the tau decay point and momentum. However, final states with large numbers of pions suffer from severe backgrounds in the LHC environment.

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2 Analysis Strategy

The analysed dataset corresponds to 5.4 fb^{-1} of pp collisions collected during the data-taking years 2016–2018. As the decays $B^0 \rightarrow K^+\pi^-\tau^+\tau^-$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow K^+K^-\tau^+\tau^-$ are reconstructed from the muonic decays of both tau leptons, the resulting final states consist of two oppositely charged muons and a kaon-pion or kaon-kaon pair.

The invariant mass of the dihadron system, $m_{h_1^+h_2^-}$, is divided into a series of bins spanning the kinematic region covering the light resonances $K^*(892)^0$ and $\phi(1020)$ up to $m_{B_{(s)}} - 2m_\tau$. This approach allows to separate regions dominated by resonant (such as the $K^*(892)^0$ and $\phi(1020)$ states) and non-resonant contributions. Three methods are then used to reduce background: requirements on reconstructed mass features, requirements on particle identification features and requirements on boosted decision tree (BDT) [37, 38] output.

Decays such as $B_{(s)}^0 \rightarrow D_{(s)}^-(\rightarrow h_1^+h_2^-\mu^-\bar{\nu}_\mu)\mu^+\nu_\mu$, which have a very large branching fraction, are removed with a requirement on the reconstructed $h_1^+h_2^-\mu^\pm$ mass to be larger than the $D_{(s)}^+$ mass. Decays of the type $B^0 \rightarrow D^-D^+K^*(892)^0$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow D^-D^+\phi(1020)$, where the D -meson decays semi-muonically, are expected to present characteristics analogous to those of signal due to their topology. Such decays are removed with cuts on the reconstructed missing mass squared and an estimate of the ditau mass squared. Both of those reconstructed mass features are obtained with a method similar to that in Ref. [14], where the proper velocity of the reconstructed B -meson candidate along the beam line is approximated as the true proper velocity.

Requirements are also applied on particle identification features to reduce misidentified background. Any remaining misidentified background is estimated from a data-driven method with dedicated control samples. Iterative unfolding [39] is used to estimate the yields (and distributions) of misidentified particles in the region of interest.

Finally, a multiclass BDT is used to separate signal from two remaining background classes: combinatorial background and semileptonic cascade background. Combinatorial backgrounds are represented with same-sign muon candidates in data (corresponding to $h_1^+h_2^-\mu^+\mu^+$ candidates and their charge conjugates), while backgrounds from semileptonic $B_{(s)}^0$ -meson decays are represented using simulated samples of the type $B_{(s)}^0 \rightarrow \bar{D}^0(\rightarrow h_1^+\mu^-\bar{\nu}_\mu)h_2^-\mu^+\nu_\mu$. Important features include topological quantities such as the estimated tau flight distance, calculated from the intersection of the $B_{(s)}^0$ -meson line of flight and the muon line of flight.

Only candidates identified as signal by the BDT (*ie.* with a signal score higher than either background score) are considered for further analysis. The presence of multiple neutrinos in the final state prevents direct reconstruction of the B -meson mass. Instead, an unbinned-likelihood fit to the BDT output score is performed to extract the signal and individual background yields for semileptonic, combinatorial and misidentified background. All yields are left floating apart from those of the misidentified backgrounds, which are constrained.

Each signal and background template is represented with a kernel density estimation [40], derived from simulated signal or background proxies. The bandwidth is optimised separately for each template, and sigmoid functions are used to ensure that the distributions go to zero at the edges of the BDT output. Normalisation is performed using the ubiquitous and well-measured $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi(\rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-)K^*(892)^0(\rightarrow K^+\pi^-)$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow J/\psi(\rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-)\phi(1020)(\rightarrow K^+K^-)$ channels.

3 Results

After applying all selection requirements and performing the BDT classification, no significant signal is observed, such that upper limits are calculated with the CL_s method [41]. Upper limits at the 90% and 95% confidence levels are shown in Table 1. The limits on $\mathcal{B}(B^0 \rightarrow K^+\pi^-\tau^+\tau^-)$

are also recast as limits on $\mathcal{B}(B_s^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+ \tau^+ \tau^-)$, using the ratio of hadronisation fractions $\frac{f_s}{f_d}$ [42], with the results shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Upper limits on the branching fractions of $B^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^- \tau^+ \tau^-$, $B_s^0 \rightarrow K^+ K^- \tau^+ \tau^-$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+ \tau^+ \tau^-$ in the analysed bins of dihadron mass at 90% and 95% CL.

Confidence level	Upper limit on $\mathcal{B}(B^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^- \tau^+ \tau^-)$				
$m_{K^+\pi^-}$ (MeV/ c^2)	[792, 992]	[992, 1330]	[1330, 1530]	[1530, 1726]	
90%	1.4×10^{-4}	2.7×10^{-5}	1.0×10^{-5}	2.7×10^{-6}	
95%	1.6×10^{-4}	3.4×10^{-5}	1.1×10^{-5}	3.3×10^{-6}	
Confidence level	Upper limit on $\mathcal{B}(B_s^0 \rightarrow K^+ K^- \tau^+ \tau^-)$				
$m_{K^+K^-}$ (MeV/ c^2)	[980, 1060]	[1060, 1200]	[1200, 1400]	[1400, 1600]	[1600, 1813]
90%	2.0×10^{-4}	1.3×10^{-4}	1.2×10^{-4}	6.8×10^{-5}	3.2×10^{-5}
95%	2.3×10^{-4}	1.5×10^{-4}	1.4×10^{-4}	7.6×10^{-5}	3.6×10^{-5}
Confidence level	Upper limit on $\mathcal{B}(B_s^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+ \tau^+ \tau^-)$				
$m_{K^+\pi^-}$ (MeV/ c^2)	[792, 992]	[992, 1330]	[1330, 1530]	[1530, 1726]	
90%	6.5×10^{-4}	1.2×10^{-4}	5.1×10^{-5}	1.7×10^{-5}	
95%	7.3×10^{-4}	1.5×10^{-4}	6.2×10^{-5}	2.1×10^{-5}	

A recasting procedure is performed to translate the limits obtained in bins of dihadron mass into limits on the resonant decays $B^0 \rightarrow K^*(892)^0 \tau^+ \tau^-$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi(1020) \tau^+ \tau^-$. This procedure accounts for the known branching fractions for the decays of the $K^*(892)^0$ and $\phi(1020)$ and, in the case of the $K^*(892)^0$, for the fraction of resonance expected in the lowest dihadron mass bin. Assuming that only the light resonances contribute in the lowest bins of invariant dihadron mass, the corresponding upper limits are then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{B}(B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^+ \tau^-) &< 2.8(2.5) \times 10^{-4} \text{ at } 95\%(90\%) \text{ CL} \\ \mathcal{B}(B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi \tau^+ \tau^-) &< 4.7(4.1) \times 10^{-4} \text{ at } 95\%(90\%) \text{ CL.} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

These limits constitute the most stringent constraints currently available on $b \rightarrow s \tau^+ \tau^-$ transitions, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Using the model and assumptions from Ref [27], limits can also be obtained on Δ^2 , where $\mathcal{C}_{9(10)}^{\tau\tau} = \mathcal{C}_{9(10)}^{\text{SM}} - (+)\Delta$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{B}(B^0 \rightarrow K^*(892)^0 \tau^+ \tau^-) &= (10.1 \pm 0.8) \times 10^{-9} \times \Delta^2, \\ \mathcal{B}(B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi(1020) \tau^+ \tau^-) &= (9.1 \pm 0.5) \times 10^{-9} \times \Delta^2. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The resulting upper limits are reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Upper limit on Δ^2 at 90% and 95% CL.

Confidence level	$B^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^- \tau^+ \tau^-$	$B_s^0 \rightarrow K^+ K^- \tau^+ \tau^-$
90%	2.5×10^4	4.5×10^4
95%	2.9×10^4	5.2×10^4

4 Systematic Uncertainties

Sources of systematic uncertainty are added in the pseudo-experiment generation when calculating the upper limit with the CL_s method. In particular each signal and background proxy

Figure 1: New physics predictions using the model from Ref. [27] and the latest $R(D^{(*)})$ results from HFLAV [43], with the latest Belle II [33] and LHCb [35] limits (at 90% CL) overlaid. The latter analysis is the subject of the present proceedings.

is sampled with replacement to account for the limited available statistics, sigmoid functions are alternatively included and excluded, and the bandwidths are varied within two standard deviations of the optimal point. Other sources of uncertainty include uncertainties due to data-simulation corrections, uncertainties on known quantities such as the branching fractions of the normalisation modes, and uncertainties on the overall signal efficiency.

The dominant source of systematic uncertainty stems from the limited size of the background proxies from which the templates used in the fits to the BDT outputs are derived. This source of uncertainty is generally of the same order of magnitude as the statistical uncertainty, making other sources of systematic uncertainty negligible in comparison.

5 Conclusion and outlook

The results reported in these proceedings correspond to searches at the LHCb experiment for the decays $B^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^- \tau^+ \tau^-$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow K^+ K^- \tau^+ \tau^-$ [35]. With the exception of the search restricted to the $K^*(892)^0$ dihadron mass region, all results are for as yet unexplored modes. No signal is observed and upper limits on the branching fractions are reported in bins of dihadron mass and, after recasting, for the $B^0 \rightarrow K^*(892)^0 \tau^+ \tau^-$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi(1020) \tau^+ \tau^-$ decays. The upper limit of 2.8×10^{-4} at 95% CL on $\mathcal{B}(B^0 \rightarrow K^*(892)^0 \tau^+ \tau^-)$ is the most stringent to date on $b \rightarrow s \tau^+ \tau^-$ transitions.

These results mark the beginning of a broader LHCb programme exploring rare processes involving $b \rightarrow s \tau^+ \tau^-$ transitions. The dominant systematic uncertainty arises from the limited size of the background proxies derived from data, such that improvements are anticipated with the increased luminosity [44] of Run 3 and beyond.

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